

Towards trustworthy artificial intelligence for decision-making: A lifecycle perspective on knowledge- and data-driven artificial intelligence systems

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ABSTRACT

Organisations increasingly use data-driven artificial intelligence (AI) systems in their decision-making processes. These AI systems may operate autonomously, support human decision-makers or increasingly act as collaborative team members. However, data-driven AI systems often function as black boxes, lacking interpretability. This poses a challenge in decision-making, as stakeholders involved in or impacted by the decision-making process frequently need to understand the rationale behind decisions. Moreover, data-driven AI systems operate without leveraging structured domain knowledge. As a result, data-driven AI systems may generate outputs that are misaligned with the decision context, objectives, or constraints, potentially leading to poor decisions or reduced trust in AI systems among users. Consequently, recent years have seen an increasing interest in integrating domain knowledge with data-driven AI. This is evident in neuro-symbolic AI, a subfield of AI that combines neural networks with symbolic AI. While this approach shows promise for enhancing the trustworthiness of AI systems in decision-making, the specific mechanisms by which domain knowledge integration contributes to dimensions of trustworthiness remain insufficiently explored. Therefore, this study reviews and integrates recent knowledge- and data-driven AI literature, along with relevant concepts for decision-making. Building on this foundation, it proposes a lifecycle framework for integrated knowledge- and data-driven AI systems for decision-making, and demonstrates its application through a healthcare application example. It further analyses the dimensions of trustworthiness for knowledge- and data-driven AI systems using the proposed lifecycle framework and application example. In doing so, this study advances the discourse on trustworthy AI for decision-making.

1. Introduction

Organisations increasingly use artificial intelligence (AI) systems in their decision-making processes. This can take on various forms, such as AI systems supporting human decision-makers, autonomous AI systems making decisions and increasingly AI systems that collaborate with humans as team members (Van Den Bosch et al., 2025). Organisations use AI systems for a wide range of decision-making tasks, such as predictive maintenance in manufacturing (Ayvaz and Alpay, 2021), fraud detection in the financial sector (Bin Sulaiman et al., 2022) or energy demand prediction (Arumugham et al., 2023). The growing dependence of organisations on AI systems in decision-making has led to increased attention regarding its impacts and implications, especially regarding the trustworthiness of AI systems (Li et al., 2023) and the resulting human trust in such systems (Gillath et al., 2021).

Significant research effort has been devoted to understanding the factors that influence human trust in AI systems, which is fundamental

for the adoption and effectiveness of these systems in decision-making (Bach et al., 2024). A system actor (including a human) who trusts another actor (which can be an AI-enabled system or component) indicates confidence that the trusted actor will behave as intended (ISO, 2020). However, trust in an AI system does not guarantee its trustworthiness. Trust can be misplaced towards non-trustworthy systems. The distinction between trust and trustworthiness is not always clearly articulated in the literature. The flourishing literature on human-centric AI emphasises the extent to which AI should prioritise human needs and well-being (Ozmen Garibay et al., 2023), emphasising also the importance of establishing human trust in AI. The risk here is that efforts to influence humans towards trusting AI systems may be pursued without due care for the factual accuracy of AI systems.

AI systems employed for decision-making are predominantly data-driven. However, they have limitations concerning their trustworthiness. A key limitation of data-driven AI systems is the lack of interpretability, exemplified by neural networks. Consider a healthcare

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professional who receives a recommendation from an opaque AI system regarding a decision that affects patients' health, without understanding the rationale behind it (Amann et al., 2022). Taking decisions on such recommendations without understanding their basis poses risks for individuals and organisations alike, affecting the quality of healthcare, but may also amplify bias in healthcare decision-making (Albahri et al., 2023). In addition to the lack of interpretability, AI systems that operate purely on data may produce outputs that, if acted upon, could be harmful to stakeholders involved in or affected by the decision-making process by ignoring domain knowledge, such as policies, guidelines, or an understanding of the decision-making context (Sirocchi et al., 2024).

Therefore, in decision-making processes, a key question is how to enhance the alignment of AI systems with domain knowledge (Li et al., 2022). Methods for integrating domain knowledge into data-driven AI systems enable the human in the loop (Emmanouilidis et al., 2019) and are relevant to this end (Dash et al., 2022; Giunchiglia et al., 2022). This is exemplified by the growing use of such systems, for instance, in industrial cases (Zampini et al., 2025). Of further relevance is neuro-symbolic AI, which fuses data-driven AI and symbolic AI (Garcez and Lamb, 2023; Hitzler, Eberhart, et al., 2022). By integrating domain knowledge with data-driven AI, outputs can be produced based on valid knowledge, supported by domain-consistent reasoning and sound explanations (Hitzler, Eberhart, et al., 2022). Therefore, AI systems that combine domain knowledge with data-driven learning present a promising approach to overcoming the limitations of purely data-driven AI (Hitzler and Sarker, 2022; Von Rueden et al., 2023) and can contribute towards trustworthiness (Agiollo and Omicini, 2023; Michel-Delétie and Sarker, 2024).

However, trustworthiness is shaped not only by the AI system's performance, such as accuracy, but also by how it is designed, developed, deployed, and operated (Li et al., 2023). A lifecycle perspective is therefore needed to understand trustworthiness as an emergent property that evolves across all stages of the AI system's lifecycle. Although the literature has started to conceptualise lifecycle approaches for AI systems and operational settings (Drobnjakovic et al., 2024), it still lacks a framework for the lifecycle of knowledge- and data-driven AI systems, which also applies to the application of these systems in decision-making. Existing lifecycle frameworks for AI systems do not provide adequate guidance for AI systems that integrate domain knowledge with data-driven learning. Rather, lifecycle frameworks are primarily tailored to data-driven AI systems, such as the lifecycle framework presented by ISO (ISO, 2023), the cross-industry standard process for data mining (CRISP-DM) framework (Wirth and Hipp, 2000) or the lifecycle framework presented by De Silva and Alahakoon (2022). This study aims to narrow this gap by proposing a lifecycle framework for knowledge- and data-driven AI systems and using this to analyse how trustworthiness manifests across the lifecycle. Accordingly, the research question asked in this study is:

'How can the lifecycle of knowledge- and data-driven AI systems for decision-making be conceptualised, and how does trustworthiness manifest across the lifecycle?'

Answering this question contributes to the literature on knowledge- and data-driven AI, AI lifecycle management and to the literature on AI trustworthiness. Specifically, this study contributes to the literature in two main ways.

1) Lifecycle Framework for Knowledge- and Data-Driven AI Systems in Decision-Making

This study proposes a lifecycle framework for AI systems that integrate domain knowledge with data-driven learning, such as neuro-symbolic AI. The framework is grounded in the literature on AI systems and decision-making. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first lifecycle framework designed explicitly for knowledge- and data-driven AI systems. The framework's practical relevance is illustrated with an application example in healthcare from the

ongoing HumAIne research project (Nicolova and Pnevmatikakis, 2025).

2) Conceptual Analysis of Trustworthiness of Knowledge- and Data-Driven AI Systems in Decision-Making. This study offers a conceptual analysis of how trustworthiness is manifested across the lifecycle of knowledge- and data-driven AI systems. This analysis draws on the characteristics of trustworthy systems as outlined in relevant standards (ISO, 2022). Linking trustworthiness with knowledge- and data-driven AI offers a fresh perspective on making the best of both humans and AI systems by integrating data and domain knowledge in AI systems for decision-making.

This study provides practitioners with guidance on adopting AI systems that integrate data-driven learning with domain knowledge. The lifecycle framework is designed to bridge the gap between technical development and operational requirements. It acknowledges the importance of domain knowledge in AI systems for decision-making and includes activities to facilitate this integration. Neglecting domain knowledge in AI systems can lead to misalignment with the decision context, poor decision outcomes and diminished stakeholder trust in these AI systems. Additionally, regulatory measures increasingly demand more transparent and accountable AI systems in industry (Aschenbrenner et al., 2024). Embedding domain knowledge in AI systems can contribute towards this objective. Although the applicability of the lifecycle framework is demonstrated through an application example in healthcare decision-making, it may also apply to other industries, such as manufacturing, energy, or the financial sector. Practitioners are encouraged to validate and adapt the proposed framework in use cases across various sectors.

To address the research question, a non-systematic literature review (Kraus et al., 2022) was first conducted and is presented in a narrative style (Snyder, 2019). This approach was selected because it allows for exploring a topic that spans multiple fields, such as knowledge- and data-driven AI for decision-making. First, an iterative keyword search was conducted in the Web of Science Core, Scopus, IEEE Xplore, and ACM Digital Library databases, for peer-reviewed publications from January 2018 to June 2025, using seed terms such as 'neuro-symbolic AI', 'neural-symbolic AI', 'informed machine learning', 'knowledge- and data-driven AI', 'AI trustworthiness' and 'AI decision-making'. Second, backward and forward citation searching was conducted to identify further relevant papers. This process continued until additional searches no longer resulted in substantially new sources. From this evolving body of literature, four themes were identified that form the main body of the literature review: (i) AI systems in decision-making, (ii) trustworthiness of AI systems, (iii) data-driven AI and (iv) knowledge- and data-driven AI (Fig. 1). The insights obtained from the literature review have informed the development of the lifecycle framework and facilitated further analysis of trustworthiness in relation to the lifecycle.

This paper is structured as follows. Section 2 provides a theoretical background on decision-making and the role of AI systems, covering decision-making structures that involve humans and AI systems, as well as trust in the context of AI systems. Section 3 addresses the trustworthiness of AI systems, examining definitions and dimensions of trustworthiness, as well as evaluation strategies. Section 4 focuses on data-driven AI systems, outlining their strengths and limitations in the context of decision-making. Section 5 focuses on knowledge- and data-driven AI, including knowledge representation and reasoning, learning, explainability and the evaluation of such systems. Section 6 introduces the lifecycle framework, demonstrates its applicability in a healthcare application example, and presents a conceptual analysis of trustworthiness. Section 7 offers a discussion, and Section 8 concludes the study.

2. Overview of AI systems in decision-making

This section discusses the current baseline on humans and AI systems in decision-making. Section 2.1 offers an introduction to decision-

Fig. 1. Overview of the topics covered in the literature review.

making in organisations. Section 2.2 discusses the use of AI systems for decision-making in organisations. Section 2.3 discusses the role of human trust in AI systems in decision-making processes.

2.1. AI systems and decision-making in the organisational context

Decision-making is fundamental to organisations and involves selecting the best course of action among alternatives to achieve desired outcomes (Lehto and Nanda, 2021). Organisations constantly face decisions that range from everyday operational decisions to strategic decisions with long-term implications. Decisions are typically categorised into three organisational levels: strategic, tactical and operational (Anthony, 1965). Strategic decisions are long-term and set the overall direction of the organisation. In contrast, tactical decisions translate these strategic goals into medium-term plans. Operational decisions, which focus on the immediate future, deal with routine processes, short-term planning, and day-to-day execution. These decisions are often made under constraints regarding time, budget, and available resources. Decisions can also be categorised according to their degree of structure (Gorry and Morton, 1971; Simon, 1987). Structured decisions are based on defined processes and use measurable criteria. In contrast, unstructured decisions involve high levels of uncertainty, requiring judgment, creative problem-solving, and often collaboration among multiple stakeholders.

Decision-making has been conceptualised as a structured, step-by-step process in the literature. From a rational decision-making perspective, Bazerman and Moore (2009) outline this process through the following steps: (i) define the problem, (ii) set decision criteria, (iii) weigh criteria, (iv) generate alternative solutions, (v) rate each alternative solution, and (vi) compute the optimal decision. A wide range of frameworks and tools exists to structure the decision-making process, including multi-criteria decision-making methods (Aruldoss et al., 2013) such as the analytic hierarchy process (Vaidya and Kumar, 2006). Decisions are decomposed into criteria, alternatives and pairwise comparisons, producing transparent weightings that facilitate stakeholder discussion. The rich literature on decision-making has further produced several theories as to how humans make decisions, with examples including rational choice theory (Scott, 2000), prospect theory (Levy, 1992), or bounded rationality, which highlights that cognitive limitations constrain the search for alternatives, leading decision makers to satisfice rather than optimise (Simon, 1972).

Recently, the rapid advancements in AI have led to such systems being widely incorporated into decision-making processes in organisations. In this study, the term 'AI system' refers to the integration of AI models, operated through supporting software, hardware, and a combination of automation and human processes. In contrast, an AI model is defined as a parameterised function $f_\theta : \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathcal{Y}$, where \mathcal{X} is an input space, \mathcal{Y} is an output space and $\theta \in \Theta$ denotes the model's parameters with Θ denoting the parameter space. For instance, in supervised learning, the parameters of f_θ are obtained by applying a learning algorithm to optimise θ using a training dataset $D = \{(x_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^n$ with respect to a loss function $L(f_\theta(x), y)$. Given this distinction, the remainder of this section focuses on the application of AI systems for decision-making in the organisational context.

AI systems enhance decision-making by providing data-driven insights and, in some cases, automating decisions (Agarwal et al., 2018). Early developments in AI systems for decision-making in the 1970s and 1980s initially focused on representing knowledge, reasoning over these representations, and deriving conclusions accordingly. Later, in the 2010s, machine learning approaches gained prominence. Machine learning includes multiple learning paradigms, such as supervised, unsupervised, and reinforcement learning (Bishop, 2006). Furthermore, semi-supervised and self-supervised learning were introduced to account for the partial or complete lack of labelled data (Prince, 2024). Further advancements led to the gradual introduction of large language models (LLMs) in decision-making processes. AI systems are also linked with existing decision frameworks from decision sciences, such as multi-criteria decision-making methods (Sahoo and Goswami, 2023; Storey et al., 2024).

The successful deployment of AI systems in organisations depends on the organisation's readiness, which is determined by factors such as strategic alignment, resources, knowledge, culture, and data (Jöhnk et al., 2021). For instance, strategic alignment may require top management support and insight into the AI system's potential business value. Adequate resources, financing, personnel, and IT infrastructure are needed for designing, deploying, and maintaining AI systems, as well as acquiring the required expertise. Organisations must build AI-related knowledge, enhance employee skills, and foster effective collaboration between AI systems and human decision-makers. Furthermore, the organisational culture, depending on factors such as interdepartmental cooperation and effective change management, is essential for overcoming resistance and ensuring that AI systems meet their objectives.

Human resistance to AI adoption can stem from various sources. For instance, humans may fear job displacement (Zhan et al., 2024) or be sceptical about the properties of AI systems, including a lack of trust in these systems (Choung et al., 2023). Finally, for the successful deployment of AI systems, data availability and quality are essential for training AI models and attaining satisfactory performance (Jöhnk et al., 2021).

Aside from internal factors influencing the adoption of AI systems within organisations, the use of AI systems for decision-making is subject to regulatory oversight. A primary concern relates to data privacy and security, as well as compliance with regulations, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), considering its impact on AI (Hamon et al., 2022). AI systems used in decision-making often rely on sensitive data. If this data is leaked or manipulated, it not only exposes risks to individual privacy but can also cause AI systems to make harmful decisions. Additionally, biases embedded in training data can lead to unfair or discriminatory outcomes (Mehrabi et al., 2021). Other data-related issues include the risk of becoming outdated, mislabelled, or incomplete, resulting in unreliable outputs of the AI system. Another issue is the question of accountability. This pertains to determining who should be held responsible for decisions made or influenced by AI (Berber and Srečković, 2024; Bleher and Braun, 2022). The negative consequences of erroneous or biased AI-driven decisions highlight the need for mechanisms to assess and mitigate associated risks. Concerns about the societal implications of AI-enabled decision-making have grown significantly in recent years, amplified by examples of AI misuse and failure (Hendrycks et al., 2023). This has led to efforts to establish regulatory frameworks to ensure the safe use of AI systems. The European Union introduced the AI Act (European Parliament, 2024), which categorises AI systems into four risk levels: minimal risk, limited risk, high risk (the primary focus), and unacceptable risk, the latter of which results in a prohibition of such AI systems. However, how regulatory provisions are to be implemented by organisations is often not sufficiently clear, creating uncertainty regarding the boundaries of AI deployment for decision-making. Having discussed the organisational context of decision-making and the use of AI, the next section explores how AI systems are incorporated into decision-making processes.

2.2. Autonomous, supportive and collaborative AI systems in decision-making

This section examines how humans and AI systems interact, collaborate, and share responsibility across various configurations in decision-making processes. Selecting the appropriate form of collaboration depends on the characteristics of the decision. Ivanov (2023) proposes a set of criteria to guide this selection, including the required speed of the decision, the negative consequences of a wrong decision by AI, the negative consequences of a wrong decision by a human, decision frequency, level of algorithmisation, context uncertainty, decision complexity, outcome uncertainty, transparency required, and the ethical issues related to the decision. Assessing these characteristics can help determine the appropriate role of AI systems and humans in the decision-making process.

The role of humans and the degree of automation in decision-making have been extensively examined in the literature. Wickens (1998), for instance, identifies ten levels of automation in decision and action selection, ranging from complete human control to fully autonomous systems. From this perspective, human-AI collaboration roughly manifests in two forms: decision support and autonomous decision-making systems. In addition to these configurations, the concept of human-AI teaming has gained attention recently (Tsamados et al., 2024). This approach depicts AI systems as collaborative partners or teammates that work alongside humans, sharing responsibilities and bi-directional learning to achieve goals (Van Den Bosch et al., 2025).

The following subsections examine these three decision-making structures (Fig. 2), which are also covered in the literature on AI-

Fig. 2. Roles of AI systems in decision-making.

based decision-making (Storey et al., 2024). Section 2.2.1 discusses autonomous AI systems for decision-making. Section 2.2.2 addresses supportive AI systems for decision-making. Section 2.2.3 examines collaborative decision configurations, focusing on human-AI teaming.

2.2.1. Autonomous AI systems

AI systems are increasingly used for autonomous decision-making, often referred to as algorithmic decision-making (Goodman and Flaxman, 2017). Autonomous AI systems operate without human intervention and are valuable in decision-making contexts that demand rapid, consistent, and large-scale decision-making. By processing data, such systems can make decisions efficiently and precisely, often surpassing human capabilities. However, the high level of autonomy also introduces challenges, especially in high-stakes decisions. Removing humans from the decision loop complicates questions of accountability, transparency, and fairness, raising concerns about the trustworthiness of such systems (Zerilli et al., 2019). Without human oversight, minor inaccuracies in training data or model assumptions can escalate into systematic failures (Kordzadeh and Ghasemaghahi, 2022; Starke et al., 2022). To mitigate these risks, some decision-making systems retain a degree of human involvement through mechanisms such as approval, intervention, or monitoring.

Recent developments in agentic AI further drive the evolution of autonomous AI systems. This reflects a shift from reactive or task-specific AI systems toward systems designed to operate as autonomous agents capable of goal-directed behaviour, self-initiated action, and adaptive decision-making (Acharya et al., 2025). Agentic AI refers to systems that possess a degree of autonomy, characterised by a capacity to make context-aware decisions, pursue objectives over time, and interact with complex environments. Unlike AI systems that respond to predefined inputs, agentic AI systems can set sub-goals, plan over extended horizons, and adjust their behaviour based on feedback and changing conditions. This is implemented by integrating LLMs, planning modules, reinforcement learning, memory mechanisms, and interaction models that simulate deliberation and choice (Acharya et al., 2025).

2.2.2. Supportive AI systems

Besides making decisions autonomously, AI systems can also be applied to support human decision-makers. These systems are designed to provide insights and recommendations to assist humans in making informed decisions (Bonczek et al., 2014). They gather, analyse, and present data in a way that helps users evaluate options and make decisions. Initially, decision support systems were designed mainly to assist managerial-level decision-making (Gorry and Morton, 1971). Today, however, AI-driven decision support tools are deployed across various organisational levels.

2.2.3. Collaborative AI systems

The relationship between humans and AI systems may shift from a traditional tool-user dynamic, such as in decision support, to a collaborative partnership. From this perspective, AI systems are not merely

instruments to be directed but also teammates capable of shaping and being shaped by human interaction. Reducing human-AI dynamics to static models or fixed roles overlooks the evolving nature of their interaction. Pedreschi et al. (2025) introduce the concept of human-AI coevolution, a feedback loop in which human behaviour and AI systems continuously adapt to one another. This perspective reframes collaboration as a bidirectional learning process, moving beyond traditional automation levels or static human-in-the-loop paradigms. As AI systems advance, there will be more opportunities for humans and AI systems to work together as team members (Schelble et al., 2024; Tsamados et al., 2024). This kind of collaboration involves mutual learning, not just about the task at hand, but also about each other and how to function effectively as a team. To support this co-learning process, it is essential that both human and AI partners can exchange knowledge and share their experiences, both in terms of the task and the dynamics of the team (Van Den Bosch et al., 2025).

Steyvers and Kumar (2023) discuss three challenges for effective human-AI collaboration, illustrated in Fig. 3. These are (i) understanding the determinants of human-AI complementarity, (ii) understanding human mental models of AI, and (iii) developing effective methods of interaction with AI.

Understanding determinants of human-AI complementarity

Achieving effective human-AI collaboration depends on understanding when the AI system can complement human decision-making (Steyvers and Kumar, 2023). The goal is to combine the individual strengths of humans and AI to exceed what can be achieved by working independently. Assessing how AI can complement human decision-making depends on the decision context and the capabilities of the human and the AI system.

Understanding human mental models of AI

The second challenge relates to understanding human mental models of AI systems. For AI to be used effectively in decision-making, humans must have an accurate mental model of how the AI system operates, including its capabilities and limitations (Steyvers and Kumar, 2023). Humans can perceive when AI is an expert or not in a particular domain, and adapt to this observation (Zhang et al., 2022). However, misunderstandings can lead to over-reliance on AI or scepticism, negatively impacting decision quality. Helping users build accurate mental models through improved transparency, feedback, and education about the strengths and weaknesses of AI systems is essential for building trust and using AI systems appropriately. Striving for AI accuracy maximisation is not always beneficial, as this might lead to a sub-optimal human-AI teaming set-up (Bansal, Nushi, et al., 2021).

Effective methods for interacting with AI

The third challenge highlighted by Steyvers and Kumar (2023) is the

Fig. 3. Three challenges in human-AI collaboration in decision-making: adapted from Steyvers and Kumar (2023).

development of effective methods for interaction with AI systems. A crucial factor is the moment when AI assistance is provided to the human decision-maker. Four categories are identified by Steyvers and Kumar (2023): (i) concurrent, (ii) sequential, (iii) on demand, and (iv) time delayed. Furthermore, it is essential to determine what information AI systems should present to humans, such as confidence levels or explanations for how AI reached its output (Steyvers and Kumar, 2023). In addition to these factors, effective human-AI collaboration depends on how users interact with AI through interfaces (Boy, 2011). The interface can be seen as a mediator between human and algorithmic decisions, affecting the humans' attachment and detachment from the decision (Bader and Kaiser, 2019).

2.3. Trusting AI systems

Regardless of the role of AI systems in decision-making (i.e., supportive, autonomous, collaborative), the extent to which users and stakeholders trust the AI system shapes their acceptance and usage of the system, as well as the overall impact on the decision-making process. Trust can be defined as 'the willingness of a party to be vulnerable to the actions of another party based on the expectation that the other will perform a particular action important to the trustor, irrespective of the ability to monitor or control that other party' (Mayer et al., 1995, p. 712). It is suggested that human trust in AI systems follows a trajectory, beginning with high initial trust, which is sustained depending on how the human perceives the AI's behaviour (Glikson and Woolley, 2020). Research has shown that when humans observe algorithms making errors, their confidence in AI systems is reduced (Dietvorst et al., 2015). Additionally, humans are more likely to develop an aversion to algorithms when they make mistakes than when they see humans make similar errors (Dietvorst et al., 2015). A systematic literature review by Bach et al. (2024) highlighted three factors affecting user trust in AI systems: (i) socio-ethical considerations, (ii) technical and design features and (iii) user characteristics, as outlined in Fig. 4.

Socio-ethical factors refer to the environment in which the AI system is implemented (Bach et al., 2024). This includes factors such as user data protection and methods of addressing human concerns related to the AI system. The second set of factors focuses on the technical and design features of the AI system. This includes, for instance, providing the user with appropriate information about the AI system and explanations for its generated output (Bach et al., 2024). The third category that influences human trust in AI systems, as outlined by Bach et al. (2024), refers to user characteristics. Building trust in AI systems varies among individuals and is influenced by a range of personal factors. Studies have indicated that a person's attachment style influences the degree of trust they place in AI (Gillath et al., 2021). Human perception

Fig. 4. Factors influencing human trust in AI systems (Bach et al., 2024).

also influences trust in AI through behavioural factors, such as offering a feeling of affect or affinity to a user (Bach et al., 2024). Complexity is also linked to trust, with evidence suggesting that humans tend to trust AI systems more with complex problems than with simpler ones, as people are often more confident in challenging AI outcomes in simpler cases (Tahtali et al., 2024).

In decision-making, AI systems' outputs contradicting human understanding can foster scepticism among humans, potentially hindering future collaboration between humans and AI systems. Adopting AI requires humans to have mechanisms to resolve such conflicts by flagging and correcting errors in the output of AI systems, ensuring, when possible, that the AI system supports rather than overrides human judgment (Kaur et al., 2023). Human reliance on AI recommendations has also been demonstrated to impact the quality of decision-making, which hinges not only on the accuracy of AI systems but also on the human ability to discern effectively when to follow or override AI advice (Schoeffer et al., 2024). However, for such human engagement with AI systems, transparency regarding how AI outcomes are produced is required.

There are several methods to evaluate human trust in AI systems. A study by Vereschak et al. (2021) investigated methods for evaluating human trust in AI systems in the context of decision-making. The study distinguishes between quantitative and qualitative methods. Quantitative methods include questionnaires and trust-related behavioural measures. Vereschak et al. (2021) identified several trust-related behavioural measures in the literature, such as the number of times humans follow the AI system's recommendation or the number of times humans ask for a recommendation. Physiological measures are also listed, such as heart rate variability and hand trajectories. In contrast to these quantitative methods, qualitative methods used to evaluate human trust in AI systems include think-aloud protocols, as well as observations and interviews with humans (Vereschak et al., 2021). Human trust in an AI system indicates a willingness to rely on it, but it does not guarantee that it is actually trustworthy. The following section focuses, therefore, on the trustworthiness of AI systems.

3. Trustworthiness of AI systems: concepts and requirements

This section focuses on the trustworthiness of AI systems. Section 3.1 provides an overview of definitions and dimensions of trustworthiness. Section 3.2 outlines evaluation strategies for the dimensions of trustworthiness.

3.1. Definitions and dimensions of trustworthiness

Trustworthiness is a fundamental concept for AI systems in decision-making. It is defined as a quality characteristic of systems and is understood as the 'ability to meet stakeholders' expectations in a verifiable way' (ISO, 2022). However, one should not confuse the standards-based established understanding of trustworthiness as an objective quality property of systems with that of trust, which is a relational concept between two actors. Trust is defined as a relational concept between two actors: the trustor and the trustee. When a system actor, including a human, trusts another actor, which may be an AI-enabled system or component, it shows confidence that the trusted party will behave as intended (ISO, 2020). In other words, a trustor trusts a trustee. However, trusting an AI system does not make it trustworthy. Poor alignment between data and domain knowledge may affect the trustworthiness of a data-driven AI system in decision-making, even if people are mistakenly led to trust AI outcomes. Conversely, a lack of trust in AI outcomes may limit adoption, even if the AI system being employed is trustworthy. Therefore, the aim is for trust to be placed in trustworthy actors, systems, or outcomes, and for actors to be guided only to trust trustworthy actors, systems, or outcomes. This requires approaches to assess AI systems' trustworthiness (Raza et al., 2025).

Alternative views on trust and trustworthiness exist in the context of

AI systems. The relationship between trust and trustworthiness of AI systems is subject to active scientific debate (Durán and Pozzi, 2025; Reinhardt, 2023). Arguments have been presented that not only trust, but also the trustworthiness of AI systems, is a relational concept. The argument provided is that contextual circumstances and different purposes of different trustors imply that a non-objective but trustor-specific understanding of trustworthiness might be more appropriate than an objective one (Wirz et al., 2025). According to this, trustworthiness is not merely a matter of objective fact but depends on perceptions. This varies depending on the trustor's evaluation of the AI system's trustworthiness for a given context, distinguishing between the use, development, and policy context. However, the view that trustworthiness is a subjective concept does not offer an actionable understanding of trustworthiness and precludes objective verification. The existing definition of trustworthiness already allows for differentiation between the expectations of different stakeholders and, therefore, different purposes. Different expectations constitute the articulation of different stakeholder requirements. The joint satisfaction, often through compromises, of the requirements posed by various stakeholders with conflicting interests, is also common in multi-stakeholder decision-making. It is handled by identifying a range of decision options that fall within the admissible space of decisions for all involved stakeholders. Otherwise, a subjective view of decision-making degenerates to individual decision-making, which, although of interest, is neither helpful nor actionable in multi-stakeholder decision-making scenarios.

According to the definition outlined in ISO standards (ISO, 2022), the dimensions of trustworthiness include accountability, accuracy, authenticity, availability, controllability, integrity, privacy, quality, reliability, resilience, robustness, safety, security, transparency, and usability (Fig. 5). This definition also applies to AI systems (ISO, 2020). However, while standards related to trustworthy AI are emerging, they are fragmented across regions and institutions and partially overlapping. In addition to the dimensions outlined by ISO (2022), several other frameworks have been proposed for trustworthy AI. For instance, the High-Level Expert Group on AI outlined seven requirements of trustworthy AI systems (European Commission, 2019). These are (i) diversity, non-discrimination and fairness, (ii) transparency, (iii) privacy and data governance, (iv) technical robustness and safety, (v) accountability, (vi) human agency and oversight, and (vii) societal and environmental well-being. Linking trustworthiness with risks, the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) introduced a risk management framework for AI systems (NIST, 2023). This framework outlines seven characteristics of trustworthy AI systems: (i) valid and reliable, (ii) safe, (iii) secure and resilient, (iv) accountable and transparent, (v) explainable and interpretable, (vi) privacy-enhanced and (vii) fair with harmful bias managed. Similarly, NASA's framework for the ethical and trustworthy use of AI systems requires them to be: (i) fair, (ii) human-centric and societally beneficial, (iii) explainable and transparent, (iv) accountable, (v) secure and safe, and (vi) scientifically and technically robust (McLarney et al., 2021).

3.2. Evaluation strategies for trustworthiness

Studies have focused on operationalising the dimensions of trustworthiness, linking them with evaluation criteria (McCormack and Bendeche, 2024). The need for comprehensive AI evaluation approaches is increased by the rapid adoption of LLMs, which generate different and diverse outputs, even with slight variations in prompting. This triggered research into the development of comprehensive evaluation frameworks for AI systems, such as Inspect AI, developed by the UK's AI Security Institute (AI Security Institute UK, 2024). A recent literature review by Kemmerzell et al. (2025) outlined evaluation criteria for the seven dimensions of trustworthiness as outlined by the High-Level Expert Group on AI (European Commission, 2019). The evaluation strategies identified by Kemmerzell et al. (2025) are listed in Table 1. The authors argued that while some strategies, such as

Fig. 5. Dimensions of trustworthiness (ISO, 2022).

Table 1

Evaluation strategies for AI trustworthiness dimensions identified by Kemmerzell et al. (2025).

Trustworthiness dimension	Evaluation strategy
Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness	Data analysis
Transparency	Group fairness evaluation
	Individual fairness evaluation
	Computational explainability evaluation
	Human-based explainability evaluation
Privacy and data governance	Openness
	Documentation review
	Input and output transparency
	Data anonymisation
Technical robustness and safety	Secure computing and encryption
	Federated learning
	Vulnerability against privacy attacks
	Access control analysis
	Privacy impact assessment
	Robustness to distribution shift
Accountability	Out-of-distribution detection
	Robustness to adversarial attacks
	Uncertainty evaluation
	Attribution analysis
	Algorithmic auditing
Human agency and oversight	Legal and regulatory compliance
	Remediation and redress mechanisms
	Impact assessments
Societal and environmental well-being	Interaction quality
	Extent of human involvement
	Carbon footprint evaluation
	Model assessment
	Computing infrastructure assessment

robustness testing, are relatively mature and supported by established quantitative metrics, others, including societal and environmental well-being, remain harder to quantify. For more details on the evaluation strategies for trustworthiness, the paper by Kemmerzell et al. (2025) offers a comprehensive overview, including aspects and metrics for each evaluation strategy, while also specifying when each trustworthiness evaluation strategy is relevant along the AI system lifecycle.

4. Data-driven AI systems for decision-making

This section focuses on data-driven AI systems in the context of decision-making, with their strengths described in Section 4.1 and the limitations highlighted in Section 4.2.

4.1. Strengths of data-driven AI

Data-driven AI systems are increasingly used in decision-making due to their ability to recognise patterns in data and compatibility across various data modalities. Such systems support evidence-based decision-making and primarily rely on machine learning techniques to infer patterns and relationships from data, rather than explicitly programmed knowledge. In this context, data encompasses structured inputs (e.g.,

tabular data), unstructured inputs (e.g., text, images, video), or time-series signals (e.g., sensor data). The effectiveness of data-driven AI depends on the quality, quantity, and diversity of the training data (Budach et al., 2022). By extracting patterns and relationships from diverse inputs, data-driven AI enables decision-makers to base their decisions on empirical evidence. Such systems can be scaled as they can process vast quantities of data beyond human cognitive limits. State-of-the-art data-driven AI systems achieve or surpass human performance in a wide range of tasks. Deep learning architectures learn hierarchical multiple levels of representation directly from raw inputs (Lecun et al., 2015). This reduces the need for manual feature engineering. Once a data-driven AI system is trained, it can be reused or fine-tuned on other datasets and diverse use cases (Zhuang et al., 2020), using cloud and distributed infrastructure to maintain performance as data grows. This allows application across different problem sizes and levels of complexity. Online or continual learning methods, although challenging, enable model updates as new data arrives, aiming to sustain accuracy and relevance without full retraining (Wang et al., 2023). Furthermore, self-supervised and generative AI techniques have gained traction recently, focusing on output generation. These systems are also being increasingly integrated with decision-making processes (Hao et al., 2024) and offer new opportunities to enhance such processes.

4.2. Limitations of data-driven AI

Despite success across domains, data-driven AI systems face limitations when applied to decision-making processes. A limitation is their dependence on large volumes of high-quality data (Budach et al., 2022). In practice, such datasets are often limited, expensive, or difficult to obtain. Furthermore, data-driven AI can inherit biases from historical data, leading to biased or unfair outcomes (Ntoutsi et al., 2020). Another limitation is that data-driven AI does not inherently incorporate domain knowledge. This increases the risk that the generated outputs deviate from established industry standards, best practices, or constraints. Additionally, data-driven AI decisions can be challenging to audit or reproduce due to the complexity of model architectures or the dynamic nature of the data (Mökander, 2023). This hinders regulatory compliance and real-world adoption.

Another limitation of data-driven AI, particularly in the context of decision-making, is its black-box nature, as exemplified by neural networks. To better understand this challenge, it is helpful to distinguish between three closely related concepts: transparency, interpretability, and explainability. Transparency refers to the extent to which the inner workings of a model are open and inspectable. Models such as linear regression or decision trees are often considered transparent. Interpretability goes a step further and focuses on how easily a human can comprehend the model's behaviour or logic. A model might be transparent yet not easily interpretable if its structure is too complex for a human to follow. Explainability, by contrast, often refers to techniques or methods developed to provide insight into AI systems that are neither transparent nor easily interpretable (Hassija et al., 2024). The remainder of this section focuses on the concept of explainability in the context of data-driven AI.

The explainability offered by AI systems regarding how their outcomes are produced is essential for both decision-makers and stakeholders to evaluate and trust AI systems in decision-making (Ferrario and Loi, 2022). While explaining decisions is a natural part of human communication, it is considerably more complex for data-driven AI. This is especially challenging for data-driven neural networks, which operate through multi-layered computational structures. Even when it is possible to trace AI outcomes to a trail of computations or through visualisations, these explanations are often not interpretable by humans, undermining trust in decision-making (von Eschenbach, 2021). Various stakeholders can participate in the decision-making process. These stakeholders might benefit from tailored explanations that align with their specific expertise and needs (Ali et al., 2023; Kim et al., 2024). The target audience of explainable AI, as described by Arrieta et al. (2020), may include groups such as domain experts, regulatory entities, management, data scientists, AI developers, and end-users of the AI system. Recent research proposed a decision support system that can guide the selection of the appropriate explainable AI method based on the stakeholders' needs (Reis et al., 2025), as well as a framework that can guide the implementation and adoption of explainable AI methods in organisations (Tchuente et al., 2024).

Current explainability approaches include model-specific and model-agnostic techniques (Dwivedi et al., 2023). Model-specific techniques are tailored to specific types of AI models. They use the model's unique architecture, features, or properties to provide explanations. In contrast, model-agnostic techniques are methods that can be applied to any machine learning model. They treat the model as a black box and analyse the input-output behaviour to generate explanations. In addition to model-specific and model-agnostic, a distinction can be made between global and local explainability. Global explainability methods aim to explain the model's overall behaviour, and local explainability methods are used to clarify specific model outcomes. Often, there is a trade-off between model accuracy and explainability (Crook et al., 2023). Simplifying models to enhance explainability can sometimes compromise their accuracy. Therefore, research on explainable AI has targeted making black-box models more transparent, and the area remains subject to active research (Saeed and Omlin, 2023).

Not all explainability techniques provide insight into how AI systems generate outputs. For instance, methods such as feature importance scores can highlight the features that influence predictions. However, they may not clarify how or why these features affect the specific model's outcomes and do not consider the dependencies between features. As a result, users might end up with a surface-level understanding, which might not empower them to make well-informed decisions based on the AI's generated output. Explainability methods that act posterior to learning from data may seek to identify explanations even when AI outcomes are wrong or data associations are not aligned with causality. Thus, explainability may deceive humans into trusting AI outcomes when this should not be the case. Furthermore, there can be a disconnect between the explanation and the actual output-generating processes of the models, which impacts the accuracy of the explanations. This misalignment may lead to user misunderstandings, making it challenging to build trust. Researchers have identified this phenomenon in LLMs, where the LLM is prompted or instructed to provide a chain of thought. Studies have indicated that the LLM-generated reasoning steps don't always accurately reflect the actual reason for the generated output (Turpin et al., 2023).

Besides the veracity of explanations, there is a concern regarding humans' reliance on AI's explanations (Nourani et al., 2021). Research has indicated that explanations provided by AI increase the likelihood of acceptance of AI's recommendations by humans, regardless of whether the recommendation is correct (Bansal et al., 2021). Humans can be influenced by misleading explanations, leading them not to check the correctness of the AI's output (Cabitza, 2024). This reliance may lead to a more passive approach by humans in decision-making, where AI outputs are accepted without sufficient scrutiny, potentially

compromising the quality of decision outcomes. Humans may over-rely on AI systems when they provide seemingly confident recommendations or under-rely when explanations are unclear or conflict with their understanding. Yet, evidence is mixed as research indicates that explanations can reduce overreliance on AI models during decision-making (Vasconcelos et al., 2023).

5. Knowledge- and data-driven AI

This section focuses on knowledge- and data-driven AI. Section 5.1 provides an introduction to knowledge- and data-driven AI. After the introduction, four core components of knowledge- and data-driven AI are discussed. These four components are presented in Fig. 6. Section 5.2 focuses on knowledge representation. In Section 5.3, learning is discussed, and explainability is discussed in Section 5.4. Finally, Section 5.5 discusses the evaluation of knowledge- and data-driven AI.

5.1. Introduction to knowledge- and data-driven AI

Recent interest in integrating domain knowledge with data-driven AI has increased. Domain knowledge integration can provide the context and reasoning capabilities for data-driven AI systems (Sarker et al., 2021). By leveraging data-driven learning alongside domain knowledge, such AI systems aim to achieve complementary advantages.

Neuro-symbolic AI is the research field in AI that focuses on integrating symbolic AI with neural networks (Hitzler and Sarker, 2022). Integrating symbolic AI with neural networks, or sub-symbolic AI, is a longstanding research goal in AI. The first studies explicitly mentioning the term neuro-symbolic AI can be traced back to the 1990s (Khosla and Dillon, 1997; Lallement et al., 1995). Recent research interest in neuro-symbolic AI has surged, as evidenced by the growing attention the topic receives in the literature. Various frameworks for neuro-symbolic AI architectures have been proposed, such as logic tensor networks (Badreddine et al., 2022), logical neural networks (Riegel et al., 2020), neural probabilistic soft logic (Pryor et al., 2022), neuro-symbolic hierarchical rule induction (Glanois et al., 2022), or neural logic machines (Dong et al., 2019). However, neuro-symbolic AI faces significant challenges. Reconciling neural networks and symbolic AI is challenging because symbols and neural networks operate on different principles. In symbolic AI, symbols are discrete entities representing explicit knowledge and are, for instance, organised as trees, databases, ontologies, knowledge graphs, or formal logic (W. Wang et al., 2022). In contrast, neural networks learn task-relevant representations as distributed, parameterised representations, acquired implicitly from data rather than encoded as explicit human-interpretable knowledge structures (Bengio et al., 2016). For a comprehensive analysis of tools and methods in the field of neuro-symbolic AI, we refer the interested reader to the literature review by Bhuyan et al. (2024).

A frequently used taxonomy of neuro-symbolic AI systems is proposed by Kautz (2022), outlined in Fig. 7. This taxonomy consists of six types and takes a high-level view of the integration of neural networks and symbolic methods. Type 1 is relatively straightforward, as in this type of neuro-symbolic AI, neural networks process vectors based on symbolic data. This is used in natural language processing and does not contain explicit symbolic reasoning. Type 2 consists of symbolic systems incorporating neural networks as subroutines. In type 3, neural networks convert data into symbols and relationships, which are then processed by symbolic reasoning systems. Type 4 involves processing symbols using a neural network trained based on symbolic rules. In type 5, neural network structures are shaped based on symbolic rules, for instance, incorporating knowledge within the architecture or loss function of the neural network. Type 6 takes this further by allowing neural networks to conduct symbolic reasoning internally. This type is interpreted by Kautz (2022) as the most promising form of neuro-symbolic AI.

Part of neuro-symbolic AI are approaches that integrate domain

Fig. 6. Components of knowledge- and data-driven AI.

Fig. 7. Neuro-symbolic AI taxonomy proposed by Kautz (2022).

knowledge at various stages of the machine learning pipeline (Gaur et al., 2022). Multiple terms are used in the literature for this purpose, such as knowledge-infused AI (Gaur et al., 2022), knowledge-augmented AI (Cui et al., 2023), knowledge-embedded machine learning (Farbiz et al., 2023) or informed machine learning (Von Rueden et al., 2023). They define informed machine learning as ‘learning from a hybrid information source that consists of data and prior knowledge. The prior knowledge comes from an independent source, is given by formal representations, and is explicitly integrated into the machine learning pipeline’ (Von Rueden et al., 2023, p.616). Multiple learning paradigms are relevant to this end, such as supervised learning, unsupervised learning, but also reinforcement learning (Silva and Gombolay, 2021).

Moreover, recent advancements in LLMs have introduced new methods for incorporating knowledge into these models. From a knowledge integration perspective, LLMs can be fine-tuned to fit specific domains, organisational contexts or industry needs. In this case, a pre-trained model f_{θ} updates its parameters on a domain dataset D_{domain} , yielding a model $f_{\theta'}$. Multiple techniques have been proposed for fine-tuning LLMs, such as full model fine-tuning or parameter-efficient fine-tuning (Wang et al., 2025). Besides fine-tuning LLMs, retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) can be used to provide context to LLMs (Arslan et al., 2024). RAG combines a retrieval function \mathcal{R} , which returns relevant documents for a query q , with the LLM, producing outputs conditioned on both q and $\mathcal{R}(q)$ (Lewis et al., 2020). Integrating domain knowledge directly relates to the trustworthiness of LLMs, which remains a vital factor influencing their adoption (Eigner and Händler, 2024), as LLMs can produce factually incorrect outputs and are prone to so-called hallucinations.

5.2. Knowledge representation and reasoning

In the organisational context, knowledge can be defined as: ‘a fluid mix of framed experience, values, contextual information, and expert insight that provides a framework for evaluating and incorporating new experiences and information. It originates and is applied in the minds of

knowers. In organisations, it often becomes embedded not only in documents or repositories but also in organisational routines, processes, practices, and norms’ (Davenport and Prusak, 1998, p.5). Knowledge must be extracted from human experts, existing repositories, or other structured sources and converted into machine-readable formats. Knowledge engineering is often labour-intensive, requiring technical expertise and a thorough understanding of the domain. Moreover, misrepresenting or oversimplifying knowledge can lead to suboptimal decision-making by the AI system, which may struggle to deal with real-world variability or edge cases that human experts understand well but are challenging to codify (Brachman and Levesque, 2004). Various types of knowledge, such as scientific, world, and expert knowledge, are being integrated with data-driven AI, as outlined in Fig. 8 (Von Rueden et al., 2023). They define world knowledge as ‘facts from everyday life that are known to almost everyone and can thus also be called general knowledge’, expert knowledge as ‘knowledge that is held by a particular group of experts’ and scientific knowledge as ‘the subjects of science, technology, engineering, and mathematics’ (Von Rueden et al., 2023, p.619).

In this study, ‘domain knowledge’ refers to expert knowledge, including organisational information, such as knowledge on products, processes, organisational policies, or industry standards. The precise scope depends on the AI system’s intended use in a given decision-making context. However, other types of knowledge, such as scientific or world knowledge, can become relevant in specific decision-making

Fig. 8. Types of knowledge integrated with data-driven AI (Von Rueden et al., 2023).

scenarios. Some AI systems integrate scientific knowledge rather than organisational or industry knowledge. Physics-informed neural networks (Cuomo et al., 2022; Raissi et al., 2019) are a prime example, as they integrate scientific laws, ensuring AI-generated output remains consistent with the principles of physics. This highlights that, while the focus of this study is primarily on domain knowledge, which reflects organisational expertise, different AI systems focus on other forms of knowledge, such as scientific concepts, which fall outside the scope of this study.

Knowledge representation and reasoning are connected. For instance, logic is used to represent knowledge, and a reasoning mechanism is used to process this knowledge and draw inferences. Reasoning involves: ‘the formal manipulation of the symbols representing a collection of believed propositions to produce representations of new ones’ (Brachman and Levesque, 2004, p.4). Two dominant approaches in AI for reasoning are logical and probabilistic reasoning (Hitzler, Sarker, et al., 2022). Logic provides a formal framework for representing knowledge and for conducting inference over it (Russell and Norvig, 2020). Three primary modes of logic reasoning are (i) deductive, (ii) inductive and (iii) abductive reasoning (Chowdhary, 2020). In deductive reasoning, the system applies general rules or premises to a specific case to guarantee a conclusion. Inductive reasoning, in contrast, derives general rules from specific observations. Abductive reasoning infers the most plausible explanation for a set of observations. In contrast to logical reasoning, probabilistic reasoning incorporates the principles of probability theory to handle uncertainty. Probabilistic reasoning involves modelling the likelihood of various outcomes or hypotheses based on available evidence. Techniques such as Bayesian networks and Markov models are commonly used to represent and compute probabilities (Russell and Norvig, 2020). Probabilistic reasoning allows for reasoning under incomplete or noisy data by providing probabilities rather than certainties. However, probabilistic reasoning faces challenges, including computational complexity and the need for an accurate representation of uncertainty.

Knowledge representation within AI concentrates on how to capture, store, and manipulate knowledge. Representation formalisms initially included forms of propositional logic (Russell and Norvig, 2020), and expanded to semantic representations such as ontologies and knowledge graphs. Sections 5.2.1 and 5.2.2 outline key concepts of ontologies and knowledge graphs.

5.2.1. Ontologies

Ontologies are formal frameworks that structure and organise concepts within a specific domain, enabling humans and machines to understand and reason about that domain. An ontology consists of five key components: (i) classes, (ii) instances, (iii) attributes, (iv) relations, and (v) axioms (Khadir et al., 2021). The process of constructing an ontology consists of seven steps: (i) task identification, (ii) assembling relevant knowledge, (iii) deciding on a vocabulary of predicates, functions and constants, (iv) encoding knowledge of the domain, (v) encoding descriptions of the problem instances, (vi) posing queries and getting answers and (vii) debugging the knowledge base (Russell and Norvig, 2020). While humans may construct ontologies, the construction can also be automated (Al-Aswadi et al., 2020). A frequently used language for creating ontologies is the Web Ontology Language (OWL) (McGuinness and van Harmelen, 2004). This language is underpinned by description logic. Description logic uses three primary components: concepts, roles and individuals. Concepts, denoted by uppercase letters such as C and D , represent classes or sets of individuals and can be combined using constructors like conjunction ($C \sqcap D$), representing the set of individuals that are both part of C and D . Disjunction is used to represent the set of individuals that are members of C or D or both ($C \sqcup D$). Negation is used to represent the set of individuals that are not part of C ($\neg C$). Individuals, denoted by lowercase letters such as a and b , are the basic objects within the domain. Roles, represented by lowercase letters like r and s , describe binary relationships between individuals.

For example, $\exists r.C$ denotes the set of individuals that are related via r to at least one individual belonging to concept C .

5.2.2. Knowledge graphs

Knowledge graphs are a form of structural knowledge representation and have been widely adopted over the past few years (Fensel et al., 2020). A knowledge graph is: ‘a graph of data intended to accumulate and convey knowledge of the real world, whose nodes represent entities of interest and whose edges represent relations between these entities’ (Hogan, 2021, p.3). A knowledge graph can be formally represented as $\mathcal{G} = (V, \mathcal{R}, E)$ where V is the set of entities, \mathcal{R} is the set of relations and $E \subseteq V \times \mathcal{R} \times V$ is the set of triples, each represented as (h, r, t) where h is the head entity, r is the relation and t the tail entity. Generally, there are two types of knowledge graphs: open knowledge graphs and enterprise knowledge graphs (Hogan et al., 2021). Open knowledge graphs are publicly available, and enterprise knowledge graphs are developed and used by organisations to store enterprise information (Hogan et al., 2021). Knowledge graphs can be constructed in several ways. Human actors can manually create them, which is a resource-intensive process. The process can also be automated to extract information from various sources, such as text files (Hogan et al., 2021). A formal methodology for knowledge graph development was proposed by Tamašauskaite and Groth (2023), comprising six steps: (i) identify data, (ii) construct the knowledge graph ontology, (iii) extract knowledge, (iv) process knowledge, (v) construct the knowledge graph, and (vi) maintain the knowledge graph.

5.3. Learning

Reasoning and learning in AI systems are connected as they can be complementary. A literature review by Yu et al. (2023) identifies three key interactions between learning and reasoning in neuro-symbolic AI, which are closely related to the neuro-symbolic AI types proposed by Kautz (2022). The interactions between learning and reasoning proposed by Yu et al. (2023) are: (i) reasoning for learning, (ii) learning for reasoning, and (iii) learning-reasoning. First, in reasoning for learning, reasoning mechanisms guide learning by providing structured frameworks or constraints that facilitate the learning process. For instance, logic can shape how models learn from data, ensuring that learned representations adhere to the logic. Second, in learning for reasoning, learning algorithms enhance the reasoning processes. An example of learning for reasoning is when neural networks are used to constrain the search space of symbolic systems. Third, in the learning-reasoning category, neural and symbolic systems interact bidirectionally and reinforce each other (Yu et al., 2023).

In addition to the categorisation of neuro-symbolic AI systems based on learning and reasoning by Yu et al. (2023), Von Rueden et al. (2023) focused specifically on knowledge integration with data-driven AI. They identified four ways to achieve this knowledge integration at specific stages of the pipeline. According to this categorisation, knowledge can be integrated into the (i) training data, (ii) hypothesis set, (iii) learning algorithm, or (iv) final hypothesis. The first integration method includes embedding knowledge by augmenting the training data. Let the original dataset be $\mathcal{D} = \{(x_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^N$ where $x_i \in \mathcal{X}$ are inputs and $y_i \in \mathcal{Y}$ are labels. Knowledge from the knowledge base \mathcal{K} can be used to enrich the training data, resulting in an augmented dataset $\mathcal{D}' = \mathcal{D} \cup \mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{K}}$, where $\mathcal{D}_{\mathcal{K}}$ denotes the set of knowledge-derived samples. The model is then trained on \mathcal{D}' instead of \mathcal{D} . The second knowledge integration method consists of techniques that integrate knowledge into the model architecture or network structure. A straightforward example is the mapping of logic gates to individual neurons (Riegel et al., 2020).

The third knowledge integration method incorporates knowledge into the learning process. For example, a term can be added to the loss function that measures how well the model’s outputs meet constraints derived from the knowledge base. The loss function can thus be

expressed as $L = L_{\text{data}} + \lambda L_{\text{logic}}$ where L_{data} denotes the standard data-driven loss (e.g., cross-entropy or mean squared error), L_{logic} captures violations of knowledge-based constraints, and $\lambda > 0$ is a hyperparameter that balances logical consistency with the data-driven loss. This approach enables models to adhere to domain knowledge that data alone might not reveal. A prominent example is the logic tensor network (Badreddine et al., 2022), which uses a differentiable first-order logic language to formulate domain knowledge and integrate it with data-driven AI models such as neural networks to optimise for knowledge satisfaction. Multiple other architectures have been proposed that incorporate knowledge into their loss function (Hu et al., 2016; Roychowdhury et al., 2021; Xu et al., 2018). The fourth method highlighted by Von Rueden et al. (2023) involves integrating knowledge into the final hypothesis. Here, the outputs of an AI model are validated with domain knowledge, to ensure compliance.

5.4. Explainability

Explainability is a central theme in research on neuro-symbolic AI (Bennetot et al., 2022; Díaz-Rodríguez et al., 2022; Mileo, 2024). A study by Calegari et al. (2020) discusses explainability for two types of neuro-symbolic AI systems: (i) integrated symbolic and sub-symbolic AI systems, and (ii) AI systems containing a symbolic and sub-symbolic component that interact but remain separate entities. In neuro-symbolic AI systems, where symbolic and sub-symbolic systems are integrated, it refers to, for example, models where logic is integrated into the loss function of a data-driven neural network. In these methods, knowledge is encoded implicitly, but the integrated knowledge, such as rules, can be used to assess how well rules are satisfied, thereby generating explanations (Wagner and Garcez, 2024). Most contemporary neuro-symbolic AI systems adopt such integrated approaches Kautz (2022). However, explainability comes at a cost. As symbolic and sub-symbolic components become more tightly coupled, the interpretability of the symbolic part reduces.

By contrast, in AI systems that contain a separate symbolic and sub-symbolic component, explainability is partly achieved by design, as the symbolic component remains directly interpretable. Calegari et al. (2020) identify two approaches to explainability in this category. The first focuses on extracting knowledge from the sub-symbolic component, which is extensively covered in recent surveys (Ciatto et al., 2024; Sabbatini, 2025). This is exemplified by research on extracting concepts from neural networks, for instance, by considering individual neurons or complete layers (Lee et al., 2025). Such methods improve the understanding of how neural networks internalise concepts, which can then be used to generate human-interpretable explanations. The second group outlined by Calegari et al. (2020) focuses on knowledge graph embedding and its use for explanations. Ontologies also play an important role in explainable AI (De Souza Ribeiro and Leite, 2021; Guizzardi and Guarino, 2024). It was argued by Confalonieri and Guizzardi (2024) that ontologies can contribute to the explainability of neuro-symbolic AI systems from various perspectives. Starting with reference modelling, ontologies provide a common shared understanding of knowledge in a particular domain. Besides this, ontologies can facilitate common-sense reasoning. Additionally, ontologies can aid in knowledge refinement and complexity management.

5.5. Evaluating knowledge- and data-driven AI

Evaluating AI systems involves quantifying the performance of AI according to appropriately defined metrics. Research on evaluating AI systems that integrate knowledge and data is relatively scarce. In a survey on the verification, validation, testing, and evaluation of neuro-symbolic AI systems, Renkhoff et al. (2024) outline two methods for assessing these systems. The first method is to verify and validate the symbolic and sub-symbolic components (e.g., neural network)

separately. This means evaluating the validity and consistency of the symbolic AI component while applying conventional evaluation techniques for the sub-symbolic component. The second option is to leverage symbolic AI to verify and validate the sub-symbolic model separately.

Evaluating data-driven AI involves assessing various aspects of the model. Zhang et al. (2022) highlight seven categories for evaluating machine learning models: (i) correctness, (ii) over- and underfitting, (iii) robustness and security, (iv) efficiency, (v) fairness, (vi) interpretability, and (vii) privacy. Correctness includes using standard performance metrics or techniques, such as mean squared error for regression or accuracy for classification tasks. Overfitting and underfitting refer to evaluating whether the model learns patterns from the training data and can generalise to unseen testing data. Robustness checking involves evaluating whether the model is robust to noise. Efficiency refers to assessing the efficiency of model training. Fairness focuses on ‘measuring, discovering, understanding, and coping with the observed differences regarding different groups or individuals in performance’ (Zhang et al., 2022, p.19). Interpretability refers to the extent to which the AI system’s inner workings can be understood. The final category is privacy and involves assessing how well the model protects sensitive data, ensuring that personal or confidential information is not exposed, misused, or inferred from the system. This includes methods such as differential privacy, data anonymisation, and secure computation to prevent unauthorised access or data leakage (Zhang et al., 2022).

In contrast to data-driven AI, the evaluation of symbolic AI requires a different approach. It focuses on other factors, such as the correctness and consistency of knowledge structures. A wide range of methods exists for evaluating symbolic knowledge. This section highlights ontologies and knowledge graphs, but providing a comprehensive review of all approaches falls outside the scope of this study. Several methods are available for evaluating ontologies, including error checking, automated validation using ontology libraries, metric-based evaluations, modularisation, and task-specific evaluation (McDaniel and Storey, 2019). Beyond ontologies, knowledge graphs also require specialised evaluation methods. Multiple methods exist for knowledge graphs, for instance, humans evaluating knowledge graphs, statistical or machine learning methods to detect anomalies or rule-based evaluation methods (Xue and Zou, 2022).

6. A Lifecycle framework for knowledge- and data-driven AI systems for decision-making

This section introduces a lifecycle framework for knowledge- and data-driven AI systems. Section 6.1 reviews related AI systems lifecycle frameworks. Section 6.2 introduces the proposed framework. Section 6.3 demonstrates its applicability through a healthcare decision-making example, accompanied by an analysis of trustworthiness.

6.1. Related frameworks

Existing AI lifecycle frameworks offer comprehensive guidance, but they are primarily tailored to data-driven AI systems. To the best of our knowledge, no framework addresses the activities of knowledge- and data-driven AI systems. Such a framework is needed, as AI systems that combine domain knowledge with data-driven learning are becoming increasingly relevant in decision-making scenarios. A lifecycle framework would support the management and governance of such AI systems with the same rigour as data-driven AI systems, while also accommodating their added complexity. The remainder of this section reviews lifecycle frameworks proposed in the literature for AI systems. The aim is not to provide a systematic account of all lifecycle frameworks but rather to summarise representative related frameworks and to build on this theory to propose a framework for knowledge- and data-driven AI systems. Table 2 summarises the related lifecycle frameworks.

Scientists and practitioners have converged on a standardised version of the AI system lifecycle processes (ISO, 2023) as one of the

Table 2
Related AI lifecycle frameworks.

Source	Framework description	Lifecycle phases
(ISO, 2023)	AI system lifecycle processes	Inception Design and development Verification and validation Deployment Operation and monitoring (linked to re-evaluation and continuous validation) Retirement
(De Silva and Alahakoon, 2022)	Lifecycle framework for AI systems	Design Development Deployment
(Wirth and Hipp, 2000)	CRISP-DM is a process model that is often adopted for machine learning projects	Business understanding Data understanding Data preparation Modelling Evaluation Deployment
(Amershi et al., 2019)	Conceptualisation of the machine learning workflow	Model requirements Data collection Data cleaning Data labelling Feature engineering Model training Model evaluation Model deployment Model monitoring
(Giunchiglia et al., 2025)	Machine learning workflow with requirements	Data curation Model creation Model training Model testing Model deployment

most comprehensive and general lifecycle frameworks. However, this standardised approach is relevant primarily to data-driven AI systems with limited guidelines for knowledge- and data-driven AI. The ISO framework (ISO, 2023) contains six phases: (i) inception, (ii) design and development, (iii) verification and validation, (iv) deployment, (v) operation and monitoring (linked to re-evaluation and continuous validation), and (vi) retirement (ISO, 2023). The inception phase involves business or mission analysis, defining stakeholders' needs and requirements, and defining system requirements. The design and development phase consists of system architecture definition, design definition, system analysis, knowledge acquisition, AI data engineering, implementation and integration. The verification and validation phase is followed by the deployment phase, focusing on deployment and transition into the operation and monitoring phase. Here, a re-evaluation is done based on the inception phase. The final phase of the framework is retirement and is concerned with the disposal of the AI system.

In addition to the ISO framework, De Silva and Alahakoon (2022) present a lifecycle framework tailored to data-driven AI. It consists of three phases: (i) design, (ii) development and (iii) deployment. The design phase encompasses activities such as defining the problem, reviewing data and AI ethics, considering relevant literature, preparing data, exploring data, and acquiring data. In the development phase (De Silva and Alahakoon, 2022), the data is processed, possibly augmented, models are trained, and benchmarking is done. Furthermore, the models need to be evaluated, and this phase focuses on explainability. The deployment phase integrates the AI system into real-world workflows while continuously assessing risks and performance. This includes evaluating secondary metrics and operationalising AI pipelines. AI systems undergo ongoing monitoring and refinement to ensure continued effectiveness and adaptability in decision-making. These stages are interdependent, requiring feedback loops and adjustments to ensure that AI systems remain relevant and accurate over time.

Furthermore, frameworks have been introduced that are not strictly lifecycle models but do address the lifecycle of data-driven AI systems to some extent. CRISP-DM is a widely used process model, initially targeted

at data mining projects and often adopted for machine learning projects. CRISP-DM is an iterative process model with six phases: (i) business understanding, (ii) data understanding, (iii) data preparation, (iv) modelling, (v) evaluation and (vi) deployment (Wirth and Hipp, 2000). Besides CRISP-DM and its extensions, a study by Amershi et al. (2019) proposes nine steps of a machine learning workflow: (i) model requirements, (ii) data collection, (iii) data cleaning, (iv) data labelling, (v) feature engineering, (vi) model training, (vii) model evaluation, (viii) model deployment and (ix) model monitoring. Besides this, a recently proposed framework outlines how domain-specific application requirements should be connected to different stages of the machine learning pipeline, while also exploring the potential role of neuro-symbolic AI (Giunchiglia et al., 2025). Although the scope is similar to the framework presented in this study, it does not take a complete lifecycle view of knowledge- and data-driven AI systems.

6.2. Proposed lifecycle framework

The proposed framework (Fig. 9) consists of six phases: (i) requirements, (ii) design, (iii) development, (iv) deployment, (v) operation and maintenance and (vi) decommissioning. While the six phases align with existing frameworks, the proposed framework addresses the challenge of integrating domain knowledge with data-driven AI. The first phase of the proposed framework, requirements, is also featured in the ISO framework (ISO, 2023) as inception, in the CRISP-DM framework, as business understanding (Wirth and Hipp, 2000) and in the framework proposed by Amershi et al. (2019) as model requirements. The design, development, and deployment phases can be traced back to the framework of De Silva and Alahakoon (2022) and these phases are also covered in the other lifecycle frameworks listed in Table 2. The next phase in the proposed lifecycle framework is operation and maintenance, which is also featured in the ISO framework (ISO, 2023). The final phase is decommissioning. Note that decommissioning is only covered by the ISO framework (ISO, 2023) in the retirement phase. The proposed lifecycle framework in this study includes a decommissioning phase because, without an explicit end-of-life stage, residual technical, legal, and ethical liabilities would remain unaddressed.

In addition to the regular lifecycle phases, the framework includes activities and factors that persist across all lifecycle stages. These activities are: (i) organisational factors, (ii) regulatory compliance, (iii) ethics review, (iv) risk assessment, (v) vulnerability and threat assessment, (vi) documentation, and (vii) controllability assessment. They are visualised in the column to the left of the lifecycle framework (Fig. 9). Organisational factors capture elements such as the internal level of preparedness for AI, the required skills, the acceptance of AI systems and the related work organisation (Jöhnk et al., 2021). Such maturity factors are unique to organisations and influence the adoption of AI systems (Uren and Edwards, 2023). Organisations with established infrastructure and processes from prior experience with AI systems might be able to integrate systems more efficiently and at a lower cost. In contrast, organisations with limited capabilities often encounter higher expenses and barriers to implementation. The second factor, regulatory compliance, highlights the importance of aligning the AI system throughout its lifecycle with regulations, and ethics review is included to remain aligned with ethics throughout the lifecycle. Risk assessment is necessary to evaluate and manage the risks associated with the AI system throughout its lifecycle. Vulnerability and threat assessment are further highlighted to analyse and manage this aspect of the AI system. Moreover, documentation is included, as this is necessary throughout the lifecycle of AI systems, such as model cards (Mitchell et al., 2019). Lastly, controllability assessment is highlighted to ensure the controllability of the AI system. Furthermore, besides these activities and factors, the framework highlights the iterative nature of the AI system's lifecycle by including feedback loops between the lifecycle phases.

Fig. 9. Proposed lifecycle framework for knowledge- and data-driven AI systems.

6.2.1. Phase 1: requirements

Identifying stakeholders is essential to ensure the AI system meets their needs and expectations throughout its lifecycle. These stakeholders may include project management, user experience designers, AI developers, domain experts, legal experts, and end-users. This also includes individuals or groups affected by the outcomes or decisions made by the AI system. Their perspectives help assess potential impacts and identify risks. The second aspect covered in this phase is establishing the decision-making mode, which involves determining the decision-

making structure (e.g., AI systems autonomously, humans supported by AI systems, or human-AI teaming) and the process by which decisions are made. Third, setting objectives ensures the AI system aligns with the organisation’s or project’s goals. Objectives guide the development process and help evaluate whether the AI system is effective. Lastly, this phase involves AI system requirements and the conditions under which it must operate.

6.2.2. Phase 2: design

The design phase starts with identifying and acquiring the data required for the AI system (Liang et al., 2022). It also includes the extraction and representation of domain knowledge in a machine-readable format (e.g., ontologies, knowledge graphs, or rule-based representations). A method must be selected to integrate domain knowledge with data-driven AI. The framework lists four options for knowledge integration: (i) embedding knowledge in the training data, (ii) modifying the model architecture, (iii) incorporating domain knowledge into the loss function, or (iv) using it to validate the model's outputs, as outlined by Von Rueden et al. (2023). The knowledge integration choices feed into the model design, which can also be achieved by following one of the six types of neuro-symbolic AI as outlined by Kautz (2022). Furthermore, the design phase highlights interaction design. The framework highlights two aspects of interaction design: (i) interfaces and (ii) explainability. First, a user interface is needed to facilitate human-AI interaction, considering human factors standards (ISO, 2016). Second, the framework considers explainability an aspect of interaction design. In addition to the explainable AI techniques available for machine learning, integrated domain knowledge can be leveraged to generate explanations (Calegari et al., 2020; Confalonieri and Guizzardi, 2024; Lee et al., 2025). Finally, the framework emphasises the design of testing processes during this phase.

6.2.3. Phase 3: development

The activities in the development process are mainly similar to established data-driven AI lifecycle frameworks, such as the framework by Amershi et al. (2019). Data undergoes pre-processing, including standard activities, such as cleaning, normalisation, and handling of missing values. After this, hyperparameter tuning and model training of the knowledge- and data-driven AI model are performed. Next, evaluation, verification, validation and testing activities are performed. Standard evaluation metrics can be employed to assess the model's data-driven performance. However, additional evaluation methods are needed since the AI system incorporates domain knowledge (Renkhoff et al., 2024). In parallel, the interface and explainability mechanism must be developed.

6.2.4. Phase 4: deployment

The deployment phase involves deploying the AI system into the operational environment. This involves creating pipelines that handle data streams, setting up processes for continuous monitoring, and ensuring the infrastructure can support the computational demands of the AI system (Paleyes et al., 2022). It further includes ensuring the security of the AI system (Hu et al., 2021). Testing in realistic scenarios verifies that the AI system behaves as intended under various conditions (Gezici and Tarhan, 2022; Myllyaho et al., 2021).

6.2.5. Phase 5: operation and maintenance

In this phase, the AI system is in active use for decision-making and is continuously evaluated. The framework incorporates human-AI interaction to address collaboration between humans and AI systems in decision-making. Furthermore, the lifecycle framework emphasises decision review and governance to outline the process of reviewing the final decision made and relating it to the AI-generated output. Performance monitoring is further needed for evaluating the AI system against its objectives and criteria. Besides this, robustness testing (Tocchetti et al., 2024) and considerations of the security and safety of the AI system are needed. This phase also may include auditing, as there may be a need for both internal audits of the AI system and external audits (Mökander, 2023). Furthermore, knowledge refinement and data updates are included in this lifecycle phase. Changing operational conditions, new data sources, regulatory requirements, and evolving domain knowledge may require adjustments to the AI model. If it has been determined that the AI model no longer operates reliably, a new AI model must be trained to replace it, thereby preventing performance

degradation. Besides retraining and replacing the old model with a new one, additional strategies are available to maintain the AI model's performance. Continual learning approaches can be implemented to adapt existing AI models by learning from new data (Wang et al., 2023). Such techniques have been explored with neuro-symbolic AI (Marconato et al., 2023), but are challenging. Furthermore, approaches to active learning can be deployed to query humans for data labelling of informative observations (Cacciarelli and Kulahci, 2024). In addition, approaches to reinforcement learning from human feedback are gaining traction, particularly within the context of LLMs, to align these systems with human preferences and feedback (Chaudhari et al., 2025).

6.2.6. Phase 6: decommissioning

Decommissioning involves shutting down the AI system as it has reached the end of its operational life. This stage ensures that the discontinuation of the AI system does not compromise data integrity, regulatory compliance, or stakeholder interests. Notifying stakeholders may be essential to inform them of the decommissioning of the AI system and its implications. A key task in this phase is the controlled shutdown of the system, which must be planned to avoid disrupting dependent processes or users. Furthermore, the domain knowledge integrated in the AI system should be documented and archived. Besides managing knowledge, data management, storage, and disposal are needed to uphold data governance principles. This includes the secure disposal of data and ensuring that stored information complies with standards, such as data retention policies or privacy regulations. Additionally, a compliance audit may be conducted to verify that decommissioning activities meet regulatory requirements and governance standards.

6.3. Application example

This section presents an application example that demonstrates how the proposed lifecycle framework can be operationalised in a decision-making context. The application example aims to clarify the lifecycle framework and does not function as a detailed case study with experimental results or assessments. Section 6.3.1 provides an outline of the application domain. Section 6.3.2 explains how the proposed framework applies to this application example. Lastly, Section 6.3.3 connects the lifecycle framework and application example with the trustworthiness of the AI system, providing an analysis of the trustworthiness dimensions outlined by ISO (2022).

6.3.1. Outline

The application example is part of the HumAIne research project (Nicolova and Pneumatikakis, 2025), which focuses on AI systems for decision-making scenarios. One of the cases of this research project focuses on neuro-symbolic AI systems for healthcare decision-making. Trustworthiness is critical for AI systems in healthcare (Bailoni and Dragoni, 2025) given the potential risks associated with such systems (van Kolschooten and van Oirschot, 2024). Research increasingly targets data-driven AI systems that integrate domain knowledge, which is essential and widely available in the medical domain (Sirocchi et al., 2024). The healthcare pilot is being developed in the HumAIne project using a co-creation approach for human-centric AI design (Waschull and Emmanouilidis, 2022). The approach incorporates the views of multiple stakeholders and aims to ensure that the AI system aligns with their perspectives. The main goal in this healthcare application is to deliver personalised recommendations that support diabetes patients in daily disease management. Data used consists of patient information, including demographic details, measurements collected over multiple months (such as daily steps and sleep), questionnaires completed by the patient regarding their lifestyle, and clinical data. The domain knowledge is collected from healthcare professionals and includes medical guidelines and recommended behaviours for diabetes patients.

Prior to HumAIne, the healthcare provider relied on separate AI systems: a data-driven system and a knowledge-based system. This

fragmented architecture resulted in inconsistent output and led to a decline in trust among healthcare professionals. The HumAIne neuro-symbolic AI system integrates both approaches into a unified model. Technically, this is achieved by integrating domain knowledge, represented through knowledge representations, with the data-driven learning model, ensuring that AI-generated outputs are aligned with domain knowledge while maintaining adaptive learning from patient data. Functionally, the system predicts whether unregulated blood glucose levels are likely to occur in the near future and generates evidence-based behavioural recommendations. Importantly, all AI-generated recommendations are reviewed by healthcare professionals before reaching patients, preserving a human in the loop. The healthcare professional decides which recommendations to send to the patient based on the AI-generated suggestions. Fig. 10 provides a high-level overview of the system's data flows, decision logic and human-in-the-loop review process.

6.3.2. Applicability of the lifecycle framework

This section maps the lifecycle framework to the healthcare example, summarising key activities per phase. Table 3 summarises the main goals, primary actors, deliverables and main risks per phase.

Requirements

In the requirements phase, structured co-creation workshops brought together stakeholders (Waschull and Emmanouilidis, 2022). The main stakeholders include healthcare providers and healthcare professionals, patients, and technical actors such as AI developers. The co-creation sessions resulted in a set of objectives and requirements for the AI system. The main goal of the AI system is to predict whether patients are at risk of future unregulated blood glucose levels. This task is subject to active research (Duckworth et al., 2024). In addition to predictive performance, requirements emphasised that the accuracy of the AI system should exceed that of a purely data-driven AI system, as well as the acceptance of AI-generated advice among healthcare professionals and patients. Further requirements specified integration with the healthcare provider's software and generation of explanations for healthcare professionals. The decision-making configuration is structured with a human-in-the-loop. Specifically, this means that a healthcare professional must validate an AI-generated recommendation before presenting it to the patient.

Design

The design phase translated the requirements into a technical and interaction blueprint. The data architecture specified the inclusion of patient data such as step counts and sleep data from wearable devices, blood glucose measurements, patient responses from lifestyle questionnaires and demographic and clinical attributes. Domain knowledge was collected from healthcare professionals through a user interface and formalised into structured knowledge representations. Several methods for integrating domain knowledge have been considered, including the

application of constraints to a neural network's loss function. This includes, among others, the design of a logic tensor network (Badreddine et al., 2022). The design phase further includes the design of compatible explainability mechanisms for the AI system. Explanations are aimed at AI developers to enhance their understanding of the AI system's inner workings, as well as for healthcare professionals during the operation and maintenance phase, to better understand how the AI system arrived at its output with support from the integrated domain knowledge. Besides designing explanations for the AI system, this phase designs the user interface, facilitating interaction between healthcare professionals and the AI system.

Development

During the development phase, data engineers and AI developers collaborate to prepare, train, and validate the neuro-symbolic AI model. Data undergoes cleaning, transformation and pre-processing. Model development follows an iterative cycle of hyperparameter tuning, model training, and validation, with computational resources (GPU/CPU) provisioned based on the data scale, complexity of the knowledge base and demands of the model architecture. Performance is evaluated using appropriate standard metrics for classification. Further evaluation involves examining the degree of knowledge satisfaction achieved by the AI model. In parallel, explainability mechanisms are implemented in line with their specified design. User interface components are developed concurrently, ensuring compatibility with the deployment environment of the healthcare provider.

Deployment

The deployment phase involves integrating the AI system into the healthcare provider's operational environment. Secure data pipelines need to be configured, and the AI system's containerised services are deployed and orchestrated using Kubernetes, which enables scaling, monitoring and resource management. Interoperability must be ensured through adherence to data exchange standards and API design, enabling communication with the healthcare provider's existing systems. Furthermore, security measures must be implemented during the deployment phase, including access control, encryption, and logging. Additionally, testing activities must be conducted to ensure the robustness of the AI system under the expected operational workload.

Operation and Maintenance

In the healthcare application example, the operation and maintenance phase has not been reached. However, during the operation and maintenance phase, the AI system will be used to generate output for healthcare professionals, which is reviewed and sent to the patient. Regularly, decisions need to be reviewed, and the performance of the AI system needs to be continuously monitored to detect performance degradation. This phase also includes regular robustness testing, safety and security checks, and auditing. Furthermore, regular checks with healthcare professionals are needed to ensure that the integrated domain knowledge remains up-to-date. Similarly, new patient data becomes available over time, and model retraining and updates need to be planned and executed in parallel with ongoing system use.

Decommissioning

The last phase to be discussed is the decommissioning phase. It includes timely communication with stakeholders and controlled disabling of the system to avoid operational disruptions. The decommissioning plan further outlines the secure archiving or deletion of data and domain knowledge in compliance with the GDPR and the healthcare providers' retention policies. This phase can also include auditing to ensure the system's retirement complies with legal obligations and organisational needs.

6.3.3. Trustworthiness analysis

This section relates the framework and the healthcare example to the trustworthiness dimensions outlined in ISO (2022). The dimensions of trustworthiness are accountability, accuracy, authenticity, availability, controllability, integrity, privacy, quality, reliability, resilience, robustness, safety, security, transparency and usability. These

Fig. 10. High-level process overview of the healthcare application example from the HumAIne project.

Table 3
Mapping of lifecycle framework to the healthcare application example.

Lifecycle phase	Main goals	Main actors	Deliverables	Main risks
Requirements	Define system objectives, gather requirements, and identify stakeholders	AI developers, healthcare professionals, project leads	Objectives, requirements, stakeholder mapping	Incomplete or ambiguous requirements, misalignment between stakeholders
Design	Specify data, knowledge, model architecture and human-AI interaction	AI developers, user experience designers, healthcare professionals	AI system design blueprint and interaction design	Poor system design, inadequate explainability, low-quality or insufficient data, ineffective knowledge transfer
Development	Train and validate the integrated model, and develop explainability mechanisms and user interfaces	Data engineers, AI developers	Trained AI system and performance report	Low model performance, overfitting, bias amplification, interface usability issues
Deployment	Integrate system into operational workflows, configure pipelines and ensure security and compliance	Software engineers, security analysts	Operational AI system, deployment logs, and security report	Downtime, insufficient robustness, security vulnerabilities
Operation and maintenance	Use, monitor, and retrain the AI system	Healthcare professionals, IT support, AI developers	Performance dashboard, audit report, updated models, and feedback loops	Performance degradation, inadequate knowledge updates, increased workload, user distrust or disengagement
Decommissioning	Retire and archive the AI system	Compliance officers	Archived data and knowledge records, compliance audit reports and stakeholder notices	Data retention violations, incomplete archival, loss of knowledge assets

dimensions are grouped into four categories: (i) governance and oversight, (ii) information and data management, (iii) system operation, and (iv) human interaction. Note that the analysis is conceptual and does not intend to make definitive claims about the trustworthiness of knowledge- and data-driven AI systems.

Governance and oversight: accountability and security

Accountability is essential throughout the entire lifecycle. It is established in the requirements phase by assigning responsibilities, reinforced during the design, development, and deployment phases through documentation, and maintained during operation and maintenance by tracking performance. Furthermore, it is necessary during the decommissioning phase. Knowledge integration in AI systems introduces additional governance requirements, such as recording sources and validation of domain knowledge. Security considerations in neuro-symbolic AI systems differ from purely data-driven AI systems. The increased complexity of AI systems that include domain knowledge may introduce new security risks throughout the system's lifecycle.

Information and data management: accuracy, integrity, privacy and quality

Accuracy can be reinforced during the design and development phase of the AI system. Knowledge integration can aid data-driven AI by providing additional knowledge about the decision context (Hitzler and Sarker, 2022), with research indicating the advantages for accuracy (Hogea et al., 2024; Llugiqi et al., 2025). Importantly, an accurate AI system will yield benefits during the operation and maintenance phase, as the generated output is used in the decision-making process. However, the AI system must be continually monitored to ensure it remains accurate over time during the operation and maintenance phases. The next aspect of trustworthiness, integrity, refers to the integrity of the AI system. This can be affected by both unintentional failures and malicious activities. Standard security measures, including 'zero-trust' provisions (Rose et al., 2020) need to be extended to AI systems, to preserve the integrity of domain knowledge and data, as well as reasoning mechanisms. These need to be designed from the beginning of life, as well as monitored during the operations phase, to ensure that adequate safeguards and mitigation mechanisms are triggered when needed. Integrity can also be viewed as maintaining behaviour consistent with established domain knowledge (Hitzler and Sarker, 2022) during the operation and maintenance phase. The next dimension, privacy, is essential throughout the full lifecycle of the AI system. It is critical to enforce privacy-preserving data handling and access controls throughout the lifecycle. The last dimension of this category is quality, which can be understood as the degree to which the system's characteristics fulfil the requirements determined during the requirements phase of the lifecycle (ISO, 2022). Consequently, quality cannot be defined in absolute terms but must always be situated within the evolving requirements of the

application domain and how the AI system contributes towards this.

System operation: availability, reliability, resilience, robustness and safety

The first dimension, availability, stems from the supporting infrastructure of the AI system. It reflects the system's ability to provide reliable and timely access to its services under different operating conditions (ISO, 2022). The next dimension, reliability, can be influenced by integrating knowledge during the design and development process, which supports consistent behaviour under normal conditions by anchoring the AI system to trusted domain knowledge. The next dimension of trustworthiness to be discussed is resilience. Integrating domain knowledge during the design and development phases can provide fallback knowledge that helps the system cope with unexpected changes during operation and maintenance. However, knowledge formalisations can be brittle and rigid, as it is generally difficult to capture all knowledge effectively (Tecuci et al., 2016), which might therefore introduce risks to resilience. Moving on to robustness, integrating domain knowledge in AI systems, as designed during the design phase and developed during the development phase, can introduce constraints that can shield the AI system from noisy or ambiguous inputs, supporting robustness during inference in the operation and maintenance phase, as indicated by Li et al. (2024) in an industrial case. For the last dimension, safety, integrating domain knowledge during the design and development phases can encode safety constraints (e.g., clinical guidelines) or guardrails, reducing risks of harmful AI-generated outcomes during inference in the operation and maintenance phase, for example, in healthcare (Sirocchi et al., 2024).

Human interaction: authenticity, controllability, transparency, usability

Authenticity can be understood as the fidelity of conveying what the system claims to be (ISO, 2022). The integration of domain knowledge during design and development can reinforce authenticity by linking the system's outputs to verifiable domain knowledge, leading to more context-aware and traceable inferences during operation and maintenance (Garcez and Lamb, 2023). The next factor, controllability, requires that the use of AI and its outcomes remain under human agency when needed. Controllability can be embedded as a system characteristic through domain knowledge integration during design and development, as domain knowledge can steer the AI system's output during operation and maintenance (Hitzler, Eberhart, et al., 2022), but also through control switches that, when triggered by humans or event detection mechanisms, offer human users control over the AI and decision system operation. The dimension of transparency can be perceived as the degree of openness of the AI system (ISO, 2022). Besides the regular information that should be disclosed about the AI system to the stakeholders, an essential aspect of this is the explanations provided by

the AI system for its output. Integrating domain knowledge during the design and development can enhance transparency by exposing reasoning paths and enabling domain-based explanations for stakeholders during the operation and maintenance phase (Calegari et al., 2020; Confalonieri and Guizzardi, 2024; Lee et al., 2025). This is also exemplified in an industrial use case by Weyns et al. (2025). The last dimension of trustworthiness to be discussed is usability. One area where integrating domain knowledge during the design and development phase supports usability is by enabling explanations based on familiar domain concepts, which can enhance human-AI interaction during the operation and maintenance phase. Usability is further linked to interfaces where humans can interact with the AI system during the operation and maintenance phase (Boy, 2011).

7. Discussion

Section 7.1 summarises and discusses the main findings of this study. Section 7.2 discusses challenges for knowledge- and data-driven AI systems in decision-making. Section 7.3 discusses the study's implications for theory, practice and policy. Section 7.4 describes the study's limitations.

7.1. Insights from the review

Recent research has increasingly focused on integrating domain knowledge with data-driven AI (Bhuyan et al., 2025; Nawaz et al., 2025; Oneto et al., 2025; Sarker et al., 2021; Von Rueden et al., 2023). The motivation is to leverage the adaptive learning capabilities of data-driven AI with the structured reasoning abilities provided by domain knowledge, aiming to improve both the quality of output and corresponding explanations (Calegari et al., 2020). This direction offers a promising pathway for enhancing the trustworthiness of AI systems. Trustworthiness is gaining relevance due to the risks of AI systems in decision-making, as well as the growing societal concerns and regulatory scrutiny, such as the European Union's AI Act (European Parliament, 2024). This study conducted a narrative literature review on knowledge- and data-driven AI systems for decision-making. Insights from the review informed the development of a lifecycle framework for knowledge- and data-driven AI systems. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first lifecycle framework for such systems. The proposed framework introduces unique activities, such as knowledge extraction and formalisation in the design phase, and considers system design when integrating domain knowledge.

The applicability of the framework was demonstrated through a healthcare decision-making example focusing on neuro-symbolic AI. This was accompanied by a conceptual trustworthiness analysis based on trustworthiness dimensions (ISO, 2022). While the healthcare application demonstrates the framework's utility in a high-stakes context, the framework's applicability may extend to other sectors, such as manufacturing (Li et al., 2025). For instance, predictive maintenance AI systems often rely primarily on machine sensor data or environmental conditions (Carvalho et al., 2019). Incorporating formalised domain knowledge, such as failure modes, patterns associated with them, or machine behaviour under different operating conditions, could strengthen the trustworthiness of such systems. Nonetheless, this requires further empirical validation of the lifecycle framework in operational settings across various contexts, including quantitative evaluation. One route for operationalisation would be to use trustworthiness metrics, possibly tailored to knowledge- and data-driven AI systems specifically (Agiollo and Omicini, 2023), across lifecycle stages. This enables empirical evaluation of trustworthiness and comparison across domains. To this end, case studies could evaluate such metrics and study how lifecycle phases and activities can be adapted and governed for various decision-making scenarios with knowledge- and data-driven AI.

The organisational context is an important factor in the successful

implementation of AI systems in decision-making (Jöhnk et al., 2021). This includes factors such as the organisation's level of preparedness, human acceptance of working with AI systems, as well as the skills and competencies required to design, develop and deploy the AI system. But also environmental factors, such as competition, regulation and the ecosystem of the organisation, as well as the technology itself, have been identified to affect the adoption of AI systems in organisations (Schwaeker et al., 2025). Part of technology is interoperability, and this is crucial for AI systems in today's digital organisational environments. Technical interoperability is necessary to enable connection with other systems, while semantic interoperability ensures that systems share common conceptual abstractions in their communication (Vernadat et al., 2025). Furthermore, specific attention must be paid to the impact of the AI system on the decision-making process itself. For instance, accuracy can be an important factor in decision-making. In cases where a black box model shows better results than a more transparent model (Crook et al., 2023), using such a black-box model may still be acceptable under certain conditions, such as for low-risk decisions. Similar trade-offs have been drawn in the literature, for example, between accuracy and time (Swaroop et al., 2024). The spread of AI systems in decision-making further highlights a reconfiguration of collaboration between human and AI systems, where domain knowledge integration can foster a shared understanding between AI systems and humans in decision-making (Emmanouilidis et al., 2025). Furthermore, the AI system must align with the decision requirements, such as speed and transparency, and consideration must be given to the appropriate level of human involvement (Ivanov, 2023), as well as alignment with existing decision-making structures within the organisation, such as multi-criteria decision-making processes.

Beyond these considerations, new opportunities and challenges for knowledge integration arise due to the developments in AI. The adoption of large-scale AI systems, which are primarily data-driven, has transformed decision-making. Nevertheless, the opacity, lack of grounding in trusted knowledge and context awareness highlight the importance of domain knowledge. This is exemplified by LLMs. While LLMs excel at generating natural language responses to user prompts, their application in decision-making contexts reveals limitations. This is exemplified by the hallucinations, where models generate plausible but factually incorrect outputs (Huang et al., 2025). This issue is amplified in specialised domains, where missing or outdated knowledge in training data can lead to wrong recommendations. Addressing this issue requires approaches for incorporating domain knowledge into LLMs. Prominent methods include fine-tuning LLMs on a specific knowledge base, or RAG, where external knowledge bases are used to generate output (Ding et al., 2023; Wu et al., 2025). In contrast, LLMs can also support the resource-intensive process of knowledge representation (Ciatto et al., 2025). To conclude, although recent advances in AI and decision-making have mainly concentrated on large-scale data-driven AI systems, the role of domain knowledge remains highly important. This presents challenges that must be addressed to ensure that AI systems are aligned with decision-making contexts and are not solely reliant on data-driven insights but also incorporate domain knowledge.

7.2. Challenges of knowledge- and data-driven AI for decision-making

Several challenges remain relevant to the trustworthiness of knowledge- and data-driven AI systems in decision-making. One of the central difficulties lies in unifying knowledge-based reasoning and data-driven learning. Knowledge-based methods and data-driven AI systems operate on different principles, namely discrete and symbolic, versus continuous and sub-symbolic principles. This makes their integration into a single architecture challenging (Bhuyan et al., 2024; Garcez and Lamb, 2023). A related challenge involves the use of soft and hard constraints. Although AI systems that integrate knowledge into their loss function are trained for knowledge satisfaction, in some models, this knowledge serves as a soft constraint, meaning there is no guarantee of

complete satisfaction (Dash et al., 2022). Furthermore, if too many constraints or rules are integrated into the model, interpretability may decrease, as it becomes more complex for a human decision-maker to comprehend.

Moreover, data-driven AI systems can often scale with additional computational resources, whereas symbolic AI systems typically face scalability limitations. Reasoning over larger knowledge bases is complex, and can therefore demand substantially more computational power (Russell and Norvig, 2020). This could lead to performance bottlenecks, increased latency in decision-making or higher integration costs when deployed in large-scale, heterogeneous environments. Beyond scaling, another challenge is the lack of standardisation. There is no universally accepted framework or architecture for combining knowledge- and data-driven methods. This fragmentation limits the broader adoption of such AI systems (Dash et al., 2022). This has implications for industry adoption, as designing and developing AI systems that combine domain knowledge with data-driven learning requires specialised expertise from AI developers skilled in knowledge representation and integration. This could lead to higher costs in developing knowledge- and data-driven AI systems, compared with widely used data-driven AI systems. Such trade-offs raise the question of whether knowledge- and data-driven AI systems are mostly suited for niche applications. Nevertheless, aspects of AI systems' trustworthiness, such as transparency and controllability, remain highly relevant in decision-making processes, especially as the risks associated with decisions increase. Therefore, a trade-off between the benefits and the added time and costs of knowledge- and data-driven AI systems compared to purely data-driven AI systems might be observed.

Furthermore, domain knowledge is not always available in the desired formats, such as ontologies or knowledge graphs (DeLong et al., 2025). Building knowledge representations is resource-intensive and requires technical and domain expertise. As noted by Tecuci et al. (2016), domain knowledge often resides with domain experts in the form of tacit knowledge, which may be challenging to convert into explicit knowledge. Also, where purely data-driven AI systems require retraining on fresh data during the operation and maintenance phase in the lifecycle, domain knowledge necessitates periodic updates to ensure it remains relevant and aligned with current domain expertise. Maintaining up-to-date knowledge ensures AI systems remain trustworthy. Finally, the context-dependency of these AI systems remains a barrier. AI systems trained on domain knowledge and datasets reflect certain assumptions, constraints, and conditions. However, when deployed in dynamic, real-world settings, the environment may differ significantly from the knowledge and data on which the system was trained, potentially leading to poor outcomes, which is problematic in decision-making contexts (Wang et al., 2022).

7.3. Implications for research, practice and policy

This section outlines the implications of the study for research in Section 7.3.1, for practice in Section 7.3.2, and for policy in Section 7.3.3.

7.3.1. Research

This study makes two theoretical contributions. First, it proposes a lifecycle framework tailored to knowledge- and data-driven AI systems. While various AI lifecycle frameworks exist (Amershi et al., 2019; De Silva and Alahakoon, 2022; Giunchiglia et al., 2025; ISO, 2023; Wirth and Hipp, 2000), these frameworks primarily address data-driven AI systems and do not explicitly incorporate the processes, challenges or design considerations related to domain knowledge integration. This study aims to narrow that gap by proposing a framework specifically for knowledge- and data-driven AI systems. Second, the study contributes to theory by offering a conceptual analysis of trustworthiness for such AI systems. Existing research on trustworthy AI often centres on algorithmic fairness, privacy, or robustness, particularly in data-centric

contexts. This study extends that perspective by analysing conceptually how trustworthiness manifests across the lifecycle of knowledge- and data-driven AI systems.

7.3.2. Practice

The proposed framework has several implications for practitioners aiming to design, develop, and deploy knowledge- and data-driven AI systems in decision-making. Adoption of such systems requires organisational readiness. In particular, organisations must recognise the value of domain knowledge integration in AI systems and overcome tendencies to rely primarily on data-driven AI systems. Successful adoption may also require investment in enhanced organisational skills, including expertise in knowledge representation and integration. Formal processes or structures facilitating communication with domain experts may be required to formalise structured knowledge representations and maintain accuracy over time. This extends to the availability of tooling to support the integration of knowledge into AI systems. Such requirements throughout the lifecycle imply greater demands on organisational skills, resources and governance mechanisms. Robust governance is required, and accountable owners could be assigned throughout the lifecycle, and controls should be implemented to monitor trustworthiness at each stage. The framework further highlights the need for tailoring human oversight to the profile of the decision. High-risk or highly regulated decisions may require slower, fully transparent human-AI collaboration, whereas low-risk decisions can be made by AI systems with greater autonomy. The impact of the AI systems must not only be measured in terms of technical performance but also through organisational outcomes such as improved decision quality or stakeholder trust. Broader evaluation criteria can help organisations demonstrate the value of integrating domain knowledge into AI systems, thereby justifying and sustaining investments in such systems.

7.3.3. Policy

The present research highlights the need to strengthen policy-making towards trustworthy AI. To this end, further attention should be paid to knowledge- and data-driven AI systems. This can include requirements for knowledge- and data-driven AI systems and their explanations, following standardised guidelines for the lifecycle management of such systems (ISO, 2023). Furthermore, there are currently insufficient provisions regarding the level of human agency and AI autonomy to be maintained in AI decision-making. There is a particular void regarding accountability and auditing, and despite requirements for the 'right to explain', this remains insufficiently covered regarding research-informed policy-making. Standardisation bodies such as ISO, CEN-CENELEC and IEEE are working towards establishing standards with safeguards guidelines for AI systems, and such standards need to be considered in future regulations. This should include the malicious use of AI to coerce people into trusting non-trustworthy AI.

7.4. Limitations

This study is subject to limitations. The literature search was not conducted according to a systematic protocol (e.g., PRISMA), which introduces potential bias and limits replicability. Furthermore, the proposed framework remains conceptual. This introduces the risk of failing to account for challenges that can arise during real-world implementation. Organisational factors and technological readiness vary across industries. Furthermore, the proposed framework is limited in terms of human competencies required throughout the lifecycle, as well as integration (e.g., with legacy systems) and interoperability requirements. The reader is referred to further work in this area on skills (Chuang, 2022; Margaryan, 2023), as well as integration and interoperability (Vernadat et al., 2025), including the role of knowledge- and data-driven AI for decisional interoperability (Emmanouilidis et al., 2025). A further limitation is that the scope of the paper does not include revisiting established multi-criteria decision-making processes, such as

analytical hierarchy processes. Such processes can be included in AI-decision-making, for example, through preferences articulation in human-centred AI decision-making (Ren et al., 2023), leading to more powerful human-machine collaborative decision-making (Ren et al., 2023). Besides this, the proposed framework has not yet undergone thorough empirical validation. While the framework's applicability has been demonstrated through a healthcare application example, this does not constitute evaluation, and further work is needed to this effect, including extension to other application domains. This may restrict the generalisability of the findings and highlights the need for studies to evaluate its scalability and relevance in industries. Finally, the trustworthiness analysis included in this study is conceptual and is not accompanied by empirical analysis.

8. Conclusions

This section provides the conclusions of the study. Section 8.1 provides the main conclusions, and Section 8.2 highlights future research directions.

8.1. Main conclusions

Organisations increasingly rely on AI systems for decision-making, but this presents challenges. These challenges relate, for instance, to the trustworthiness of such AI systems in decision-making, as well as to trust issues regarding how humans place their trust in these systems. Additionally, there are risks associated with employing AI systems in decision-making. History has highlighted failures of AI systems that operate without an appropriate understanding of the context in which they are applied. Furthermore, issues arise when humans cannot comprehend how AI systems generate their outputs. Motivated by these challenges, there has been a recent increase in interest in integrating domain knowledge with data-driven AI. Observing this growing interest, this study reviews and integrates the literature on these systems, linking them to decision-making contexts. This led to the proposal of a lifecycle framework that conceptualises the lifecycle phases and activities of knowledge- and data-driven AI systems. This framework also enabled an analysis of how trustworthiness manifests throughout the lifecycle. This analysis approaches trustworthiness as a non-static property. It uses trustworthiness dimensions related to governance and oversight, information and data management, system operation, and human interaction, as outlined by ISO standards. In this sense, the study tightens the link between two research areas, namely knowledge- and data-driven AI and trustworthy AI. The lifecycle can serve practitioners and researchers in developing AI systems that integrate domain knowledge. By making explicit the role of domain knowledge integration, the framework anticipates a paradigm shift in how AI is designed for decision-making. This development is needed in decision-making, as domain knowledge is required to inform decisions and provide explanations to stakeholders. Researchers and practitioners are invited to validate the proposed lifecycle framework across industries.

8.2. Future research directions

Future research should operationalise and empirically validate the proposed framework in decision-making contexts. One immediate step in the current research plan is to conduct case studies in manufacturing, automation, and energy services. A related direction for future research is how humans can be led to trust trustworthy AI systems, or conversely, how to guard against untrustworthy AI systems, which will require a reconciliation of the currently separate handling of trust and trustworthiness. Linking knowledge with data-driven AI is beneficial to this end by explicitly embedding domain knowledge and contributing to stakeholders' trust in human-AI teaming through explainability (Paleja et al., 2021).

Related to trust is the broader issue of human agency. Future work

must clarify the appropriate level of human agency in AI-enabled decision-making and better understand which mechanisms, such as sliding autonomy frameworks, best ensure that agency (Kioskli et al., 2024). Equally pressing for human agency in decision-making with AI systems is the question of fault. When an AI-driven decision causes harm, how should responsibility be attributed, and what auditing and accountability structures are required (Zhou and Joachims, 2023)? Furthermore, part of the challenge lies with a poor understanding of the dynamics of human-AI interaction in decision-making. Human-machine teaming and its underlying interaction dynamics have been studied particularly in relation to robotics, software agents, and associated hardware automation (Johnson et al., 2012), showing the value of establishing shared context for team success (Lawless, 2020). Human-AI teaming interaction dynamics and the emergent nature of such teaming outcomes are not yet well investigated, and further research will be needed to understand and operationalise such human-AI teaming for decision-making across domains (Lawless and Moskowitz, 2025).

The organisational context further shapes these challenges. Knowledge- and data-driven AI systems require a higher level of maturity of AI readiness in organisations. Without such maturity, there is a risk that organisations will fall back on purely data-driven AI systems. Showing the added value of knowledge- and data-driven AI systems involves some level of human expertise, implying more substantial organisational commitment. This can encourage organisations to overcome knowledge, resources, and cultural barriers (Schwaake et al., 2025) in advancing towards AI adoption, which is not only data-driven but also grounded in sound domain knowledge. Such maturity advancements would be necessary for the strategic adoption of sound AI practices in organisations, especially in small and medium-sized enterprises (Al-Kfairy, 2025). There is growing evidence pointing towards the importance of systematically building AI capabilities in organisations in their pursuit of further digital transformation strides, including AI agents (Voudouris, 2025) together with alignment with AI regulation, improvement of AI governance, AI risk management, and growing AI literacy in organisations (Kubilay and Celiktas, 2025). This paper contributes to the argument that further studies and demonstrations are required to show that investments in organisational maturity must include an enhanced understanding of the value of integrating domain knowledge into AI systems.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Christos Emmanouilidis: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Sabine Waschull:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Conceptualization. **Emiel Miedema:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Investigation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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